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Solar photocatalysis as a solution for tackling Microplastics in Waste water

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Abstract:

The presence of microplastics in marine waters was increasingly documented to be a hot subject nowadays due to the evidence that they are accumulating and thus, they can move through natural food webs, which means microplastics and associated pollutants have the potential to move into human food chains, plus the imposed strict regulations in developed countries beside the moral deterrent against the natural aquatic life. The treatment of those molecules via photodegradation over Zinc Oxide (ZnO) semiconductor had been studied in this project. Here we report the fabrication of visible light active zinc oxide nanorods (ZnO NRs), wherein the visible light absorption is enhanced by a Tin Oxide coating. Methylene Blue and Coumarin had been used as an organic model to study the different photodegradation aspects. The role of the coating is to provide stability for our semiconductor in acidic pH and to enhance the degradation of organic molecule by applying the band match theory to assure a targeted flow of charge carrier between our nanorods particles in a most beneficial way to the aimed photodegradation. Results presented here provide a simple strategy to make the wide bandgap ZnO NRs visible light active, enabling their use as promising semiconductors for photocatalytic decontamination of refineries waste water.

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List of symbols and abbreviations

MP: Microplastics

PE: Polyethylene

PP: Polypropylene

PVC: Polyvinyl Chloride

AOP: Advanced Oxidation process

CB: Conduction band

CV: Valence Band

MB: Methylene blue

NRs: nanorods

ZnO: Zinc Oxide

SnO_x: Tin Oxide

DFT: density functional theory

ϕ : represents the work function

x : represents the electron affinity

E_c : represents the conduction band position

E_F : represents Fermi level position

E_v : represents the valence band level

E_g : Band gap

POPs: persistent organic pollutants

Liste des symboles et des abréviations

MP: Microplastiques

PE: Polyéthylène

PP: Polypropylène

PVC: Chlorure de polyvinyle

AOP: processus d'oxydation avancée

CB: Bande de conduction

CV: Bande de Valence

MB: Bleu de méthylène

NRs: nanorods

ZnO: Oxyde de zinc

SnO_x: Oxyde d'étain

DFT: théorie fonctionnelle de la densité

ϕ : Fonction de travail

χ : Affinité électronique

E_c : représente la position de la bande de conduction

E_F : représente la position de niveau de Fermi

E_v : représente le niveau de la bande de valence

E_g : bande interdite

POP: polluants organiques persistants

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Introduction:

In a world trembling as the economical crises drive millions in the African continent, South America... down to poverty threshold, and as well as the extremism and terrorism currents bring a devastating war to the unstable areas in the middle east, Africa... A hidden menace to the entire human species is stealthily swimming underneath the oceans. It is not the Loch Ness monster that we are talking about, or a nuclear submarine, it is a very well engineered molecule designed to be stable for hundreds of years and even more, it is the ubiquitous synthetic Microplastics.

Throughout the last 30 years, Microplastic pollution has become a major concern, especially in marine ecosystems [1], thus, it was estimated that total Plastic Produced in a year is roughly the same weight as the entire humanity [2] and to make the problem worse, it was reported that only 30% of produced plastic worldwide is only recycled [3]. Today, plastics are one of the most common and persistent pollutants in ocean waters and seas worldwide [4] as well as its existence in freshwater [5]. In the study by Thiel et al. [6] anthropogenic debris was one of the three major flotsam categories (32.4 items per km²); more than 70% of the floating debris was made up of plastic items.

Plastic debris steadily fragments into smaller pieces, forming microscopic particles of less than 5 mm, which are categorized as MP [7]. Due to their tendency to accumulate marine debris. Moreover, tracking accumulations in beach sediments is a suitable way for monitoring microplastics [8-14]. Nowadays we can see many islands, acting as sinks for ocean-borne plastics, which have already been heavily impacted by plastic debris originating far from their shores [15]. For example, the abundance of microplastic was studied in eighteen shores across six continents and ranged from 2 (Australia) to 31 (Portugal, UK) fibres per 250 mL sediment [16]. Therefore, going a slightly deeper in the core of the dilemma, the mechanism of polluting any water by plastics is often referred to polymers which contain plastic additives (PAs); for color modification (pigments and dyestuffs), mechanical properties improvements (fillers and reinforcements), resistance to heat and aging (antioxidants and stabilisers), resistance to light degradation (UV stabilizers), flame resistance improvement (flame retardants), processing characteristics (recycling additive) and performance improvement (anti-static/conductive additives, plasticisers, blowing agents, lubricants, mould release agents, surfactants, preservatives) of the polymer; [17] in addition to mechanical effects, MP may have toxic or endocrine effects due to the presence of PAs [18-19].

Inadequate removal of MP (categorized as organic molecules) in wastewater treatment plant by conventional treatment methods has forced researchers to develop alternative treatment approaches. Advanced oxidative processes (AOP) are successful in removing complex organic contaminants because they can achieve complete oxidation [20]. AOP offer a distinct advantage over many conventional treatment methods, such as biological processes, because faster degradation rates are accomplished and contaminants are degraded rather than transferred from one phase to another. In addition, there is no requirement for by-product disposal [21].

An ideal photocatalytic material would combine high photocatalytic activity with high efficiency of solar energy conversion. It should also be non-toxic, biologically and chemically inert, and stable over long periods, readily available and easily processable. However, no currently existing material or system satisfies all these requirements. Moreover, although the power delivered to the Earth from the Sun (around 1.5 10⁵ TW) exceeds that consumed by human civilization (around 13 TW), only a fraction of this energy is harvested by current photocatalytic materials, which typically have solar photo-conversion efficiencies of < 5% [22]. However, among various metal oxides, ZnO is regarded as a credible alternative semiconductor material owing to its distinct advantages of higher electron mobility than traditional TiO₂, easy fabrication routes of these nanostructures and easier modifications of the surface structure [23-26].

Chapter 1: Microplastics threatening for aquatic life...Human species and Advanced Oxidation Process (AOP) as a proposed technology to tackle the issue.

1.2A brief history of plastics

FIG.1 Norwegian petrochemical industry when the site at Rønningen in Bamble municipality opened in 1969 [27].

A world without plastics, or synthetic polymers, may look out of reality nowadays, yet their first production on large-scale was reported back to ~1950. Despite of the fact that the first made plastic from synthetic components (thermosetting phenol formaldehyde resin, formed from a condensation reaction of phenol with formaldehyde) appeared in the early 20th century, a widespread use of plastics out of the military sector did not occur until after World War II. The rapid growth in plastics production is terrifying, surpassing most other man-made materials (Notable exceptions are materials that are used extensively in the construction sector, such as steel and cement) [28-29].

FIG.2 Global primary plastics production (in million metric tons) according to industrial use sector from 1950 to 2015 [30].

Moreover, packaging is the biggest consumer of plastics (an application whose growth was accelerated by a global shift from reusable to single-use containers) Fig. 2 which has reflected in the detected plastics in municipal

solid waste (by mass) and thus, increased from less than 1% in 1960 to more than 10% by 2005 in middle- and high-income countries [31]. Accompanied by an increase in global solid waste generation [32].

FIG.3 Global primary plastics production (in million metric tons) according to polymer type from 1950 to 2015 [30]

The vast majority synthetic plastics falls into the three well know polymers: high-density polyethylene (PE), low-density and linear low-density PE, polypropylene (PP) and polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) [30] Fig. 3. None of them is biodegradable. As a result, they accumulate, rather than decompose, in landfills or natural environment [33]. Pyrolysis still the most common used way to eliminate plastics. Thus, near-permanent contamination of all natural environment with these last is a devastating concern. Plastic debris has been found in all major ocean basins [33], with an estimated 4 to 12 million metric tons (Mt) of plastic waste generated on land entering the marine environment in 2010 alone [31] Fig. 4. Contamination of freshwater systems and terrestrial habitats is also increasingly reported [34-35], as is environmental contamination with synthetic fibers [36-37]. Plastic waste is now so ubiquitous in the environment that it has been suggested as a geological indicator of the proposed Anthropocene era [38].

FIG.4 Annual global primary and secondary plastic waste generation TW (t), recycling RW (t), incineration IW (t), and discard DW (t) (in million metric tons) from 1950 to 2014 [30].

1.3 The amphibious danger

FIG.5 Microplastics from source to food chain [39]

As humanity came to a time when one of the most chemically stable organics (synthetic polymers) is produced on an extensive large scale; estimated as the same weight of the entire humanity Fig. 6 [40]; the real danger comes from our food chain. Thus, recent research shows that plastic pollution is also present in freshwater systems at concentrations equal to or greater than those documented in the world's oceans [41-44].

FIG.6 Global annual plastics production [40]

i. Source of an unseen threat

FIG.7 Plastics bags captured floating underneath water surface [45]

Microplastic migration through natural food webs become an evident truth [46-49]. Although, to date, the sources of marine MP are still not very well characterized. A rough estimation predicts that 70% to 80% of marine litter, most of it plastics, originate from inland sources and are emitted by rivers to the oceans [50]. Potential sources include wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), beach litter, fishery, cargo shipping, and harbors [50-54]. Although data is so far unavailable, runoff from industrial plastic production sites may be an additional source. Taken into consideration, recent marine studies refer to inland waters as main sources (indeed they are rather transport pathways), while actual data is still scarce [34].

Moreover, Inland sources of MP still are investigated thoroughly. However, major contributors will likely include WWTPs and runoff from urban, agricultural, touristic, and industrial areas, as well as shipping activities. Another potential source is sewage sludge that typically contains more MP than effluents [55]. Sewage sludge is still frequently used for landfilling and as fertilizer in agriculture, and surface runoff may transfer MP to rivers and lakes and ultimately river basins and the sea. Washing clothes [16] and personal care products [56] are sources of MP in WWTPs.

However, inspite of the scarcity of a large-scale study, many documentations have been reported. Thus, Napper et al. [57] estimated that thousands of microplastic beads are released by using as little as 5 mL of facial scrub exfoliants once each day with size ranges from 8 μm to >2000 μm Fig. 8 (Around 93% of the ‘microbeads’ used in cosmetics are polyethylene (PE), but they can also be made of polypropylene (PP), PE terephthalate (PET), polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) and nylon [58]).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

FIG.8 (a) Microplastics beads in facial scrub [43], (b) Estimates for the number of PE microbead particles in six brands of facial scrubs per 1 mL where product sizes are as follows: A: 163.82 μm / B: 326.83 μm / C: 317.91 μm / D: 288.80 μm / E: 289.63 μm / F: 293.48 μm [57], (c) (d) Blue and orange coloured beads [56].

Thus, Rochman et al. [59] estimated that total daily microbead release into aquatic environments may be as high as 8 trillion microbeads day⁻¹.

Wastewater treatment plants were not designed to remove this pollution during treatment [5, 60]. When MP are transported through treatment facilities via industrial effluent or wastewaters they discharge into receiving waters [56, 61]. New studies suggest atmospheric deposition may also be a significant source of microplastic fibers [62].

Urban River is contributing to the global microplastic lifecycle in term of transportation [63], and urban populations (human and aquatic species) may be subject to adverse health effects associated with this pollution. Mainly discharges from wastewater treatment plants [5], atmospheric deposition [64], and non-point sources such as combined sewer overflows (CSOs) and urban runoff [44, 64] are identified as major source of freshwater pollution with micoplastics. However, research documenting MP in freshwaters is recent, and so the full extent of environmental impacts associated with this pollution are not well understood [34].

ii. Impact on aquatic life, Microplastics as a vector for other pollutants

a. Direct Impact

FIG.9 Schematic illustration of the dynamic changes experienced by microplastic in the water [65].

Microplastics have been documented in fin fish and shellfish tissues [46, 66-69], which means MP and associated pollutants have the potential to move into human food chains Fig. 10. In addition to the chemical composition of the various types of MP and/or compounds resulting from environmental breakdown of plastics, there is also the potential for persistent organic pollutants (POPs), particularly those that are hydrophobic, to attach themselves to plastic particles [70-72]. POP transport via microplastic adsorption is most probably a function of POP concentrations, local environmental conditions, and the microplastic composition [72]. However, data describing

the risk to biota from chemical and physical properties associated with microplastic particles is currently lacking [73].

FIG.10 Sources, transport, and potential bioaccumulation of microplastics associated persistent organic compounds (POPs) released into the environment [74].

In addition, Sanchez et al. [68], investigated gudgeon (*Gobio gobio*) caught in 11 French streams and found MP in the digestive tract of 12% of the fish. Although again very preliminary, this field report shows that freshwater species ingest MP. However, the rate of MP ingestion in different fish species will certainly depend on their feeding strategy. Moreover, Rosenkranz et al. [75] demonstrate that the water flea *Daphnia magna* rapidly ingests MP under laboratory conditions. MP (0.02 and 1 mm) appear to cross the gut epithelium and accumulate in lipid storage droplets. This is of specific concern because MP infiltrating tissues might induce more severe effects Fig. 11.

FIG.11 Uptake of 20- (a, c, e, g) and 1,000-nm (b, d, f, h) fluorescein isothiocyanate–labeled polystyrene beads in neonate (<24 h old at start of experiment, a–d) and adult (e–h) *Daphnia magna* over 24h as observed by confocal microscopy. Shown are pictures after 30-min (a, b, e, and f) and 12-h exposure (c, d, g, h) [75].

FIG.12 Microplastic particles (yellow) can cross from the digestive system into the blood cells (green) of mussels [76].

Hence, Imhof et al. [77] report that intake of MP by annelids (*Lumbriculus variegatus*), crustaceans (*D. magna* and *Gammarus pulex*), ostracods (*Notodromas monacha*), and gastropods (*Potamopyrgus antipodarum*). While the available studies demonstrate that a broad spectrum of aquatic taxa is prone to MP ingestion, the toxicological effects remain uninvestigated for freshwater species.

FIG.13 Micrographs: (a) fluorescent PET MFs ($23 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$) at 515–560 nm excitation; (b) fluorescent PP MF ($28 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$) at 450–490 nm excitation; (c) fluorescent Nylon MFs ($10 \times 40 \mu\text{m}$; yellow arrows) in the intestinal tract of a 50 h.p.f. brine shrimp (*Artemia* sp.), with 515–560 nm fluorescent excitation [78].

b. Impact projection: accumulating other contaminants

The large surface-to-volume ratio and chemical composition of MP, leads to waterborne contaminants accumulation including metals [79] and persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic compounds (PBTs) [80]. A review on the relationship between plastic debris and PBTs has been published recently [81] such as dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) or polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs). Therefore, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) has been also reported to be attached to MP [82, 83], as well as Nonylphenol and bisphenol A [84–86]. However, there is a lack of information on other important contaminants like pharmaceuticals and endocrine-disrupting compounds (EDCs) although, various plastic additives in MP, including some well-known EDCs (e.g., phthalates) have been detected by Fries et al. [87]. Since the spectrum of contaminants is different in freshwater and marine systems, the chemical burden of freshwater MP remains to be studied.

The interaction between MP and other contaminants has been studied in adsorption-desorption experiments [88, 89]. While there is significant complexity in this interaction, MP contribute in transferring environmental contaminants from water to biota. While different modeling studies arrive at contrasting conclusions [70, 80, 90],

a recent experimental study demonstrates that fish exposed to contaminants sorbed to MP accumulate these compounds and suffer adverse effects such as glycogen depletion and histopathological alterations [67]. However, still not enough and a verification of the ‘vector hypothesis’ would have major ecological implications, it deserves further investigation, especially in a freshwater context.

c. Impact projection: carrying of exotic species and pathogens

FIG.14 (a) Examples of epiplastic diatoms (Diatoms were the most abundant, widespread, and diverse group of plastic colonizers) (b) Examples of epiplastic coccoliths and dinoflagellate (c) Examples of epiplastic rounded, elongated and spiral cells.[91]

The risk in contained in and sorbed to MP and thus sorbed to biota overlap the possibility of developing microorganisms and biofilms on these same MP. Only very few studies have been conducted on this issue with marine ecosystems being the focal point of interest [92, 93].

FIG.15 Light micrograph of nano-scale plastic particles aggregated in seawater due to the ‘stickiness’ of EPS. Photo by DR. Steve Summers (a Postdoc Fellow in the Gutierrez Lab who is currently working on the RealRiskNano project (<https://epaquatic.org/realrisknano/>)) [94]

A study by Zettler et al. [93] reports that several plastisphere members are hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria which may potentially influence plastic debris fragmentation and degradation as well as Reisser J et.al. [91] Fig. 14. However, they also found opportunistic (human) pathogens like specific members of the genus *Vibrio* dominating plastic particles. Therefore, MP can act as a vector for waterborne (human) pathogens influencing the hygienic water quality. The fact that the microbial communities on MP are distinct from surrounding water (only some

marine bacteria develop biofilms on microplastic particles [95]) suggests that MP serve as a kind of new habitat. Until now, the complex interaction between microorganisms/microbial communities as a key player in aquatic ecosystems/food webs and MP, especially in freshwater, is poorly understood and needs to be further investigated.

1.4 Advanced oxidation process (AOP)

Advanced oxidation process relies on the photodegradation of targeted organics using a semiconductor that provide much faster degradation rate, so, organics molecules are mineralized to CO₂ and water instead of transferring the pollutants from one phase to another [96]. The first trials to use a semiconductor to proceed a photodegradation was reported in 1938, when the photobleaching of dyes by TiO₂ semiconductor was studied by Doodeve et al [97]. Since that year, the field has experienced major developments every ten years till 1970 when the first water photo-electrolysis was done by Honda–Fujishima effect (Honda–Fujishima effect) in the early 1970s.

In our modern days, AOPs requires three main components [96] such as:

- 1) Semiconductor's photocatalyst
- 2) Light energy (UV or visible or solar)
- 3) Electron donor or hole acceptor.

In photocatalytic reactions, liquid or gas phase reactants and/or products come into contact with the light-absorbing semiconductor photocatalyst. Hence, the semiconductor material can be activated by photons with sufficient energy equal to or greater than the band gap energy (E_g) (energy difference between the conduction band and valence band of the material) [98].

However, when the semiconductor photocatalyst is illuminated with a light energy greater than its band gap, a charge carriers (i.e., electron-hole pair) are produced followed by initiation of reduction or oxidation reactions which ultimately generate hydroxyl radicals $\bullet\text{OH}$ and superoxide anions $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ in the system so these two will start a mechanism that will lead to the transformation of organic compounds and other organics to intermediates molecules first and these intermediates will transform to the final product: CO₂ and H₂O Fig. 16.

Fig.16 Schematic diagram of photocatalytic reactions for the degradation of organic contaminants [99].

Efficient photocatalytic processes have the potential to yield major steps forward in tackling some of society's greatest challenges; most prominently in meeting clean energy demand and tackling environmental pollution. Photocatalysis applications of far-reaching importance include water splitting for hydrogen generation [100-102], degradation of environmental pollutants in aqueous contamination and wastewater treatment [103-107], carbon dioxide remediation [108], self-cleaning activity [109,110] and air purification [111]

Chapter 2: Comparison between the most widely used semiconductors and photocatalyzed degradation of Microplastics from the band theory perspective

2.1 Comparison between the most widely used semiconductors leading to the choice of ZnO

The commonly used metal oxide semiconductor photocatalysts are titanium dioxide (TiO₂), zinc oxide (ZnO), tungsten oxide (WO₃), strontium titanate (SrTiO₃), and hematite (α -Fe₂O₃) [112]. Most of these semiconductor photocatalysts, except hematite, have a band gap in the ultraviolet (UV) region, i.e., equivalent to or larger than 3.2 eV ($\lambda=387$ nm), and promote photocatalysis upon illumination with UV radiation [113]. The limited amount of UV light in the sun's spectra (around 7%) stands as a big obstacle in the direct use of solar energy for photocatalytic decomposition of organic and inorganic contaminants.

Photocatalysis using titania received much attention after the successful photolysis of water using TiO₂ photoanode upon irradiation with UV light with wavelength smaller than 190 nm in 1972 [114]. The widely used titania nanoparticles (Degussa P25) in an aqueous colloidal dispersion show optical absorption peaking at around 220 nm with near zero absorption after 370 nm [115]. The reaction photoefficiency of the titania nanoparticles is very low, [116] which has been attributed to the scattering of light by the TiO₂ particles [117]. However, TiO₂ is not very active as a visible light photocatalyst. Visible light photocatalysis can be activated in metal oxide semiconductors (such as TiO₂ and ZnO) through the presence of the inherent defect states in the nanocrystallites. Defect states can be created intentionally within the band gap through doping with transition metals.

With a large number of active sites, ZnO exhibits very high surface reactivity, rendering it an efficient visible light photocatalyst as compared to TiO₂. High reaction and mineralization rates [118] in ZnO photocatalysis have been reported due to the efficient generation of hydroxyl [119]. Surface and core defects in nanoparticles play a vital role in photocatalysis reactions (in ZnO, there is a multiplicity of levels, some deriving from residual impurities, some from oxygen deficiency, and others related to topographical irregularities [120]).

Thus, our choice for ZnO as the used semiconductor in photocatalysis is based on its reported advantages over TiO₂ in addition of its reported characteristics which will be widely investigated in chapter 3.

2.2 ZnO photocatalyzed degradation of Microplastics from the band theory perspective

Fig.17 Illustration of theoretical occupied bands by electrons (Band Theory) [121].

The mechanism of any photocatalysis process is mainly owing to three critical related steps [122] Fig.17:

- (i) light absorption and charge excitation
- (ii) Charge separation and transport from the semiconductor particle to its surface-active sites.
- (iii) Surface photocatalytic chemical reactions, and this process is similar to the fundamental mechanism of photocatalysis in power systems.

Typically, as we can see in Fig. 17 when a semiconductor is irradiated with an incident light with energy greater than the band gap, an electron-hole pair with specific reduction and oxidation potential will be created on its conduction band (CB) and valence band (VB). Here, the band gap of the semiconductor determines the utilization rate of the energy of the incident light, and the CB and VB values are the origin of the reduction and oxidation abilities of the photoexcited electron and holes [122].

However, in practical process, the performance of photocatalysts is mainly related to two conditions:

- (i) The energy ($h\nu$) of the incident photon should be larger than the energy gap (E_g) of the photocatalyst.
- (ii) The redox potential of reactants should be located between the CB and VB of the semiconductor photocatalyst.

Fig.18 Band positions (top of valence band and bottom of conduction band) of several semiconductors together with some selected redox potentials. [123].

On the one hand, the former condition indicates a narrow band gap, which can facilitate the efficient utilization of incident solar-light. On the other hand, the latter condition demonstrates that a higher CB potential and a lower VB potential, which are thermodynamically beneficial for the reduction and oxidation reactions of the reactants, respectively. But a high CB and low VB potential means a broad band gap of a photocatalyst, which leads to the poor solar-light utilization as discussed in condition (i). It is obvious that these conditions above are mutually contradiction, and it is important to find the balance point to design the photocatalyst. However, for a single component photocatalyst, it is difficult to possess both wide light absorption range and strong redox ability concurrently. Besides, in the single-component structure, the photogenerated electrons in the CB can easily return to the VB or trap in the defect state and recombine with the holes, which seriously reduces the utilization efficiency of solar energy [124]. So to avoid the excited- state conduction-band electrons and valence-band holes recombination we have the following destinations as choices:

- 1- To get trapped in metastable surface states.
- 2- To react with electron donors and electron acceptors adsorbed on the semiconductor surface or within the surrounding electrical double layer of the charged particles.

Thus, if a suitable scavenger or surface defect state is available to trap the electron or hole, recombination is prevented and subsequent redox reactions may occur. The valence band holes are powerful oxidants depending on the semiconductor and pH), while the conduction-band electrons are good reductants [125].

Most organic photodegradation reactions utilize the oxidizing power of the holes either directly or indirectly; however, to prevent a buildup of charge one must also provide a reducible species to react with the electrons [126]. However, in very small semiconductor particle suspensions both species are present on the surface. Therefore, careful consideration of both the oxidative and the reductive paths is required.

Based on the above, proposed primary steps in ZnO photoelectrochemical mechanism are illustrated as follow:

Fig.19 Illustration of polymer photodegradation

- (1) Microplastics adsorbtion on the semiconductor and formation of charge carriers by a photon
- (2) Charge carrier recombination to liberate heat

(3) Initiation of an oxidative pathway by a valence-band hole and (4) initiation of a reductive pathway by a conduction-band electron

(5) Further thermal (e.g., hydrolysis or reaction with active oxygen species) and photocatalytic reactions to yield mineralization products and desorption from the semiconductor

2.3 Microplastics adsorption on the semiconductor and formations of charge carriers by a photon and charge carrier recombination to liberate heat

As, we mentioned in the introduction of this chapter when our semiconductor is irradiated with an incident light with energy greater than the band gap an electron-hole pair with specific reduction and oxidation potential will be created on its conduction band (CB) and valence band (VB). However these pairs of electron-holes, has the tendency to recombine and to go back to their initial energy state as illustrated in Fig. 20 and Fig. 21.

Fig.20 illustrated the diffusion of both species (e^- and h^+) to the interfacial surface on one hand and on the other hand the recombination of those two species before reaching the surface [124].

Fig. 21 Electron-hole recombination can occur at the surface (reaction (a)) or in the bulk (reaction (b)) of the semiconductor. At the surface of the semiconductor, photogenerated electrons can reduce an electron acceptor A (reaction (c)) and photogenerated holes can oxidize an electron donor D (reaction (d)) [127].

2.4 Initiation of an oxidative pathway by a valence-band hole and Hydroxyl radical formation and initiation of a reductive pathway by a conduction-band electron and Oxygen reduction

a)

b)

Fig.22 (a) $>ZnOH$ represents the primary hydrated surface functionality of ZnO, ecb^- is a conduction-band electron, h_{vb^+} is a valence-band hole, Red is an electron donor (Le reductant), Ox is an electron acceptor (l'oxidant), $\{>Zn^{\cdot+}OH\}^*$ is the surface-trapped VB hole (i.e., surface-bound hydroxyl radical); and $\{>Zn^{\cdot-}OH\}$ is the surface-trapped CB electron. Figure a) is based on Carp et al. 2004 figure noted as figure (b).

Therefore, as we mentioned due a sufficient light energy hitting our semiconductor, we obtain e^- and hole pairs. Thus, the photogenerated electrons lead to the formation of superoxide anions ($\cdot O_2^-$), hydrogenperoxide molecules (H_2O_2), hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot OH$), hydrogen dioxide anion (H_2O^-) and the hydroperoxy radicals ($\cdot HO_2$) [128, 129] through the following mechanism [130] (MO represent a Metal oxide like ZnO):

While the oxidation reactions initiated by the photogenerated holes are:

The reactions are terminated as:

Hydroxyl radicals are formed on the surface of ZnO by reaction of holes in the valence band (hvb) with adsorbed H₂O, hydroxide, or surface group (>ZnOH) [131, 132]. The same time the photogenerated electrons are reduce enough to produce superoxide (•O₂⁻). This superoxide is an effective oxygenation agent that attacks neutral substrates as well as surface-adsorbed radicals and/or radical ions.

Hence, According to [133] a reasonable assumption is that both photocatalytic oxidative and reductive reactions occur simultaneously on the TiO₂ particle, while otherwise charge would have built up, Which is also predicted to be the same for ZnO, Fig. 22. Therefore, two critical processes determine the overall quantum efficiency of interfacial charge transfer [133]:

- The competition between charge-carrier recombination and trapping (picoseconds to nanoseconds).
- The competition between trapped carrier recombination and interfacial charge transfer (microseconds to milliseconds).

An increase in either charge-carrier lifetime or the interfacial electron-transfer rate is expected to lead to higher quantum efficiency for steady state photolysis.

2.5 Further thermal (e.g., hydrolysis or reaction with active oxygen species) and photocatalytic reactions to yield mineralization products and desorption from the semiconductor

FIG.23 Photodegradation mechanism of polypropylene [134]

Photodegradation of organic molecule was well studied and showed that OH radicals is capable to initiate a degradation process of these molecules through a radical mechanism [135-140]. Therefore, the OH radical contributes to the formation of alkyl radicals (R•), step (1) in Fig. 23. The alkyl radicals react quickly with O₂ molecular to produce peroxy radicals (ROO•), and with other polymer chains to promote multiple chain scissions, step (2). In a next step, the peroxy radicals can react with polymer chains to form chemical species with hydroperoxide groups (ROOH), step (3). Due to hydroperoxide compounds are unstable, they can react quickly with oxygen to form organic compounds of low molecular weight such as ketones, acids, alcohols and esters, step (4). Photo-oxidative degradation of polymer can follow this mechanism to yield compounds with lower molecular weight and, finally, CO₂ and H₂O, step (5).

Chapter 3: ZnO properties affecting directly Microplastics photodegradation

Here, in our study we are more concerned in the properties of ZnO which affect the photodegradation of Microplastic molecules and the other organic pollutants. Between these properties, it comes first the crystallinity and particles size.

First, for a better understanding for the consequences of crystallinity and particles size or the others follow properties, we will briefly pass by the theory of photocatalysis degradation using a semiconductor Fig.39.

Fig.24 Photodegradation of organic pollutants [141].

Fig. 24 shows that, when an atom of semiconductor is irradiated with a photon that has as energy $E(\text{Joules})=h(\text{J.S})\nu(\text{s}^{-1})$; h is Planck's constant and ν stands for frequency; higher than the energy value of its band gap, which is noted as E_g (energy difference in electron volts between the top of the valence band the bottom of the conduction band) an electron will pass from the valence band to the conduction band [142] leaving a hole in the valence band (VB) which will be an oxidation site and an electron in the conduction band (CB) which will be a reduction site.

Thus, the photogenerated electrons in the CB can easily return to the VB or trap in the defect state and recombine with the holes, which seriously reduce the utilization efficiency of solar energy [141]. The pollutant species will undergo an oxidation or a reduction, depending on its natural state (if it has the tendency to lose an electron it will be oxidized, if it has the tendency to gain an electron it will be reduced).

So, here comes the role of many characteristics related to the crystal itself, energy state ect... Thus, we start with crystallinity and crystal size.

3.1 Crystallinity

High photocatalytic activity is associated with high crystallinity and high surface area, since they respectively prevent the electron–hole recombination and the increase of reactant quantity onto the photocatalyst surface [143].

Hence, recent studies showed that the photocatalytic activities of this sort of material are greatly influenced by the particle size and crystallinity [144] hence, Yoshiaki Sakatani et al 2005 showed that MB photodegradation using TiO₂ films calcined at various temperatures under UV light irradiation had the optimal activity at 600 °C heat treatment and the lower temperatures gave a lower photocatalytic activity due to the amorphous structure of TiO₂ films. Thus, increasing the heat treatment temperature which will increase the film crystallinity, and crystal size has led to a better photodegradation results [144] fig. 25.

FIG.25 Photodegradation of MB over TiO₂ films calcined at various temperatures under UV light irradiation [144].

The aforementioned results can be explained by the charge carrier mobility, thus, as the particles become more crystallized (the atoms become arranged in a regular, periodic manner) the mobility of charges will be easier which will allow them to reach the organic molecule (MB in this case) instead of being recombined, therefore, TiO₂ amorphous structure leads to this recombination of the photo-generated electrons. Hence, Joydeep Dutta in his paper in 2016 [145] has confirmed this relation between crystallinity and the photodegradation activity for our material (ZnO) fig. 26 when he has shown that constant rate of the photocatalytic degradation activity of ZnO nanorods increases with increasing heat treatment to have an optimal value at 250 °C than it decreases after this value due to state defect which we are going to discuss in this chapter in part c.

FIG.26 Photocatalytic degradation profile of 10 M methylene blue (MB) and 10 ppm phenol in aqueous solution under visible light irradiation with ZnO NRs photocatalysts annealed at different temperatures (90, 150, 250, 350 and 450 °C for 1 h). (a) Degradation kinetics of MB; (b) degradation rate constants of MB; (c) degradation kinetics of phenol and (d) degradation rate constants of phenol [145].

So, to deeply explain this relation between crystallinity and photodegradation activity we have to refer to two main parameters:

a) Charge carriers mobility

b) Crystal's band gap

a) Charge carriers mobility

It is well known that enhancing a crystal's crystallinity, will facilitate the movement of a charge carrier between the crystals forming the whole material (that would be our film this study) and to investigate this theory, measuring the charge carriers mobility for the same material annealed at different temperature would give us a good evidence. Thus, T.K. Roy et al in 2013 has measured in his study the relation between the ZnO resistivity and the treatment temperature (which is directly related to crystallinity). The ZnO was a powder of 99.998% purity (Alpha Aesar, Johnson Matthey) and the resistivity of the ZnO samples was measured by the standard D.C. four probe techniques. The lead connections were made onto the sample surface in a line by depositing Au–Pd alloy from a Sputter coater unit (SC7620, Polaron, UK). Silver paste was used to connect the copper wires on the spots for electrical connection; the measured lead resistance was less than 0.1 Ω . A constant current source (Keithley model no. 6221) and a nanovoltmeter (Keithley model number 2182A) were used in the resistivity measurements. The temperature dependent (30–550 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, dispersion $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$) resistivity of the sample was measured by placing the sample inside a small tube furnace [146].

FIG.27 Electrical resistivity of ZnO as a function of temperature [146].

Fig. 27 shows the electrical resistivity of the sample from room temperature to 550 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The as-received ZnO sample shows a resistivity of 0.75 M Ωm at room temperature. The evolution of resistivity with temperature, as shown in Fig. 27, has three different distinct regions. In region 1, the resistivity of the sample is observed sharply decreasing with temperature from room temperature to 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The sample exhibits NTCR (negative temperature coefficient of resistance) character in this region. On further heating, the resistivity of the sample starts increasing with a maximum resistivity of 1.5×10^{-3} M Ωm at around 420 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in region 2. The change in resistivity is observed to be from 0.5 K to 1.5×10^{-3} M Ωm within a temperature span of about 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. In this region, sample shows PTCR (positive temperature coefficient of resistance) behavior. In region 3, a decrease in resistivity with an increase in temperature

(i.e. NTCR behavior) is observed for the sample up to the present experimental range. This result seems to be in agreement with Dutta's study where he had obtained the optimal value of MB degradation at 250°C [145] nearly the same as the optimal temperature for resistivity which is claimed to be 300°C [146].

b) crystal's band gap

Zinc oxide is an n-type well-known semiconductor with a wide range of applications in catalysis, solar cells, as a gas sensor and in semiconductor devices. It manifests typical semiconductor properties, wide band gap (~3.3 eV at 300 k), large exciton binding energy (~60 meV). [147] fig. 28.

FIG.28 Evac represents the vacuum energy level, Ec represents the conduction band energy level, Ef represents the Fermi energy level, Ev represents the valence band energy level and Eg represents the band gap energy level.

The influence of the band gap on the photocatalytic activity of ZnO and its relation with manipulating the heat treatment temperature was investigated by V. Rogé al in 2015 in his study where he measured the band gap of ZnO thin films (grown as compact grains) versus this heat treatment temperature [148] fig. 29.

FIG.29 Plots of ZnO films grown at different temperatures (50 °C, 100 °C, 150 °C, 200 °C, and 250 °C) [148].

At ambient conditions, the thermodynamically stable phase is wurtzite. The zinc-blende ZnO structure can be stabilized only by growth on cubic substrates, and the rocksalt NaCl structure may be obtained at relatively high pressures. Therefore, the rocksalt structure of ZnO is obtained by using high pressures of 9.0– 9.5 GPa experimentally [151].

It has been also reported that cubic ZnO films with a zinc blende structure could be grown using ZnS (001) buffer layers on GaAs (001) substrates [152]. Therefore, the aforementioned study, reports that the ZnO film grown on the Pt (111)/Ti/SiO₂ /Si substrate with an annealing temperature above 700 °C exhibits a zinc blende structure. It is also found that we could suppress the formation of the zinc blende structure by using the Pt (111)/TiO₂/SiO₂ /Si substrate instead of the Pt (111)/Ti/SiO₂/Si substrate and obtain only wurtzite structure. Consequently, ZnO crystal structure is strongly related to the substrate on which it is deposited.

Thus, for example Y. Yoshino, K. Inoue, reported in their study in 2002 that C-axis orientation of ZnO thin films on Ni, Cu and glass is greatly influenced by the surface morphology and that on Al and Au is strongly influenced by the surface crystallinity of substrates. Also, crystallinity of ZnO on Au is better than other metals. So, for making oriented ZnO thin films both the relationships between surface morphology of substrates and substrate surface crystallinity are very important [153] which confirms that ZnO crystal orientation depends on the substrate on which the film is deposited.

But our study is concerned in ZnO films deposited on a transparent substrate which allows for the light to be transmitted through for example a glass substrate SiO₂. Thus, the hexagonal structure of ZnO deposited on a cleaned glass substrate is confirmed by T. Bora et al. [145] and of the same semiconductor deposited on FTO is confirmed by J.S. Wellings and N.B. Chaure in their study [154] and by Jingbin Han, Fengru Fan [155].

Hence, Joydeep Dutta and Sunandan Baruah in their study in 2009 reported that The ZnO crystal is hexagonal wurtzite and exhibits partial polar characteristics with lattice parameters $a = 0.3296$ and $c = 0.52065$ nm. The structure of ZnO can be described as several alternating planes composed of tetrahedrally coordinated O²⁻ and Zn²⁺ stacked alternately along the c-axis [156], as shown in Fig. 31.

Fig.31 The wurtzite structure model of ZnO [156].

Thus, referring to the aforementioned study, another important characteristic of ZnO is polar surfaces. The most common polar surface is the basal plane (0001). One end of the basal polar plane terminates with partially positive Zn lattice sites and the other end terminates in partially negative oxygen lattice sites. The oppositely charged ions produce positively charged Zn-(0001) and negatively charged O-(0001) surfaces, resulting in a normal dipole moment and spontaneous polarization along the c-axis as well as a variance in surface energy. To maintain a stable structure, the polar surfaces generally have facets or exhibit massive surface reconstructions, but ZnO \pm (0001) surfaces are exceptions: they are atomically flat, stable and exhibit no reconstruction.

The other two most commonly observed facets for ZnO are $\{2\bar{1}10\}$ and $\{0\bar{1}10\}$, which are non-polar and have lower energy than the $\{0001\}$ facets [157].

3.2 Optical properties

Since, the band gap effect on photocatalytic activity was explained in this chapter [paragraph 3.1 part b](#)) the other parameter affecting this activity is the thickness of our film.

a) Thickness effect on absorbance:

Y-Q Cao et al in 2015 has investigated this relations using ZnO thin films (grown as compact grains) and plotting Photodegradation curves of MB with respect to the irradiation time using ZnO ultrathin films with different thicknesses on Si exposed to the UV light [149] [fig. 32](#).

FIG.32 (a) Photodegradation curves of MB with respect to the irradiation time using ZnO ultrathin films with different thicknesses on Si exposed to the UV light. (b) Photodegradation efficiency as a function of the ZnO film thickness [149].

The results of the optimal thickness for the ZnO films giving the better MB Photodegradation (28 nm) was also deeply investigated and explained that the thickness is affecting the semiconductor band gap and this relation with the photodegradation activity was explained in this chapter [sec. 3.1 part b](#).

FIG.33 (a) UV–visible absorption spectra of as-deposited ZnO ultrathin films with various thicknesses on fused quartz. (b) Band gap of ZnO ultrathin films as a function of the film thickness. The inset is the band gap determination plot of 28 nm thick ZnO ultrathin film [149].

Therefore, the room-temperature UV–visible absorption spectra of as-deposited ZnO ultrathin films with various thicknesses on fused quartz plates were measured, as illustrated in Fig. 33a. For the direct band gap semiconductor, the relation between the absorption edge and the photon energy ($h\nu$) can be written as follows [158]:

$$(\alpha h\nu)^2 = A(h\nu - E_g)$$

Where A is the absorption constant of the direct band gap semiconductor material. The absorption coefficient (α) is determined from the scattering and reflectance spectra according to Kubelka–Munk theory. The direct band gap energies estimated from the intercept of the tangents to the plots are presented in fig. 33b.

The band gap of ZnO ultrathin films decreases from 3.30 eV to 3.21 eV with the film thickness increasing from 7 nm to 28 nm. When the film thickness exceeds 28 nm to 42 and 70 nm, the band gap become large to 3.22 and 3.28 eV. The as-deposited 28 nm thick ZnO ultrathin film has the smallest band gap of 3.21 eV, as shown in the inset of fig. 33b.

Why would the band gap decrease initially and then increase with the film thickness?

We think that two factors might affect the band gap of ZnO ultrathin films: the size effect and film crystallinity. Here, the film thickness plays a unique role in influence the band gap of ZnO ultrathin films. One hand, compared to bulk materials, the band gap energy of ultrathin films will increase due to the quantum confinement effect. So the band gap tends to decrease with increasing the film thickness. On the other hand, the crystalline films have larger band gap than amorphous ones which was explained before in this chapter. Usually the crystallinity of ZnO ultrathin film will be improved with increasing the thickness. That is to say, the band gap will become large with increasing the film thickness. Therefore, a tradeoff in thickness must be achieved. Finally the 28 nm thick ZnO ultrathin film exhibits a smallest band gap [149].

3.3 Defects in ZnO and doping agent

The first section of this chapter has shown that ZnO has a bandgap of 3.37 eV without modification which in the ultraviolet (UV) region. Therefore, they promote photocatalysis upon illumination with UV radiation.

Unfortunately solar spectrum consists only 5–7% of UV light, while 46% and 47% of the spectrum has visible light and infrared radiation, respectively [159]. This minimal extent of UV light in the solar spectrum has particularly ruled out the use of natural source of light for photocatalytic decomposition of organic and inorganic contaminants and bacteria disinfection from water and air on large scale. So, our semiconductor (ZnO NR) cannot absorb the visible region of sunlight (~45% of the solar spectrum) [145] this drawback is typically overcome by modifying the ZnO surfaces with visible light active materials [160-162], doping [163] or engineering the defects within the ZnO crystal [164-166]. Prior reports from Dutta group have demonstrated that defect centers in ZnO can be controlled by annealing at different temperatures [167, 168] or by simply modulating the growth rate of the nanostructures [164]. The defects which can be vacancies, interstitials or substitution type defects, create intermediate electron and hole traps between the valence band (VB) and conduction band (CB) leading to a reduction of energy required for exciton pair generation, rendering the materials visible light active [169, 170]. Although ZnO is intrinsically defective upon synthesis, these defects are typically deep with high formation energies [171] and need to be engineered to effectively contribute to the charge separation process upon light absorption.

Defects:

a) Oxygen and zinc vacancies:

Oxygen vacancies and zinc interstitials are two predominant intrinsic defects which are reported to be favorable for photocatalysis [171-173]. However, the formation of these defects is largely governed by the synthesis environment, where a zinc rich environment typically leads to oxygen vacancies and zinc interstitials and an oxygen rich environment leads to zinc vacancies and oxygen interstitials [174, 175]. Association of electrons/holes trapped in these defects with surface adsorbed oxygen and hydroxyl species, leads to the formation of O_2^- , $\bullet OH$ and other oxygenated radical species [176, 177] which are very effective in degrading contaminants in water.

Hence, T. Bora, et al in 2016 has investigated these two defects in crystals ZnO NR (in my study I followed the same procedure in preparing my ZnO NR) annealed at different temperatures (90, 150, 250, 350 and 450 °C) for 1 h. Thus, UV/Vis optical absorption and photoluminescence (PL) were performed, as shown in Fig. 34:

FIG.34 (a) room temperature UV/Vis optical absorption and photoluminescence (PL) spectra of the ZnO NRs obtained with excitation wavelength of 325 nm and (b) variation in the visible emission peak from the ZnO NRs annealed at different temperatures (c) Energy level diagram showing some of the principal defect levels in ZnO [145, 178].

The PL spectrum obtained with 325 nm excitation wavelength showed peaks in both UV and visible region, wherein the peak at 360 nm is assigned to the direct radiative recombination of electrons from the CB to the VB, representing the bandgap of the ZnO NR's [179]. The peak at 390 nm is attributed to the radiative recombination of electrons captured in defect states just below the CB with the holes in the VB of ZnO. Deep level zinc interstitial (Zn_i) defects located at ~ 0.22 eV below the CB of ZnO are reported to lead to the violet emission [180].

The broad visible emission from ZnO commonly attributed to the surface defects (mostly oxygen vacancies) [181, 182] can be resolved into two Gaussian components centered at 533 and 585 nm. Both singly and doubly charged oxygen vacancies (Vo^+ and Vo^{++} respectively) are considered to be responsible for the visible (green) emission from ZnO [183, 184]. It is generally agreed that transition of a photo-excited electron from the CB of ZnO to a Vo^{++} center causes the 533 nm emission, while the recombination of a captured electron from Vo^+ state to a VB hole leads to the 585 nm emission [185]. Also, it has also been reported that the Vo defects lead to a bathochromic shift of the ZnO NR absorption edge, increasing the visible light absorption by the NR's [186].

FIG.35 (a) In-plane diffusion and out-of-plane diffusion of oxygen vacancies in the ZnO wurtzite crystal, (b) expanded view of the ZnO wurtzite unit cell structure and defect migration, where pink arrows show in-plane diffusion and green arrows show out-of-plane diffusion. (c) Oxygen 1s (O 1s) X-ray Photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra of as-prepared and annealed ZnO NRs. The O 1s spectra are fitted with three Gaussian peaks denoted as O_a, O_b and O_c. In the lower right, the variation in the intensity of the O_b peak with respect to different annealing temperatures of the ZnO NRs is shown[145, 178].

Annealing in ambient conditions was followed to alter the density of surface defects in ZnO nanostructures [167]. Fig. 34b shows the variations in the green emission band of ZnO NRs with different annealing temperatures. For annealing temperatures up to 250 °C, the intensity of the green emission was found to increase, indicating an increase in the defect density on the NR surface. This trend has been primarily attributed to the temperature mediated diffusion of oxygen vacancies through the bulk ZnO lattice, wherein the self-diffusion of the vacancies increases with temperature [187]. The diffusion in wurtzite structure mainly occurs in two ways: in-plane diffusion along the (001) plane where there are six symmetrical paths to the next neighboring oxygen atoms and out-of-plane diffusion where six equivalent paths exist with components parallel to the [0001] axis (schematically represented in Fig. 35a). Since the oxygen *hcp* lattice in ZnO wurtzite crystal ($c/a \sim 1.606$) is smaller than the ideal wurtzite structures ($c/a \sim 1.633$), anisotropic diffusion of the defect states is dominant in ZnO [187]. This causes migration of oxygen vacancy states (Fig. 34b) from the bulk towards the surface of the NRs, resulting in a relative increase in the surface defect concentration, which is a maximum for the 250 °C annealed ZnO NRs. Upon annealing the NRs further, the non-stoichiometry at the surface of the NRs is compensated by oxidation induced by oxygen from the air, leading to a reduction of the green emission as observed in Fig. 34b [188].

In order to further explore the chemical oxygen states at the surface of the ZnO NRs, we recorded XPS spectra of the NRs annealed at different temperatures and followed the evolution of the asymmetric O 1s peaks. Annealing induced variations in the oxygen chemical states have been previously shown to result in band bending at the surface of the NRs [168]. Fig. 35c shows the asymmetric O 1s peaks from ZnO NRs annealed at different temperatures, where the O 1s peak was coherently fitted by three Gaussian components, O_a, O_b and O_c centred at 530.5, 531.7 and 532.7 eV, respectively. The O_a peak at 530.5 eV

can be attributed to Zn-O bonding, where O atoms are surrounded by Zn atoms with the full supplement of the nearest-neighbor O atoms [189]. The Oc peak at 532.7 eV is usually associated with chemisorbed H₂O molecules or dissociated O₂ or OH species on the surface of ZnO [189, 190]. The Ob component at the binding energy of 531.7 eV is reported to be associated with the O₂⁻ ions that are in oxygen-deficient regions within the ZnO matrix, typically representing the oxygen vacancy states [191, 192]. The intensity of the Ob peak therefore can be correlated to the oxygen vacancy states at the surface of the ZnO NRs. The maximum intensity of the Ob peak was observed for the ZnO NRs annealed at 250 °C, indicating the highest concentration of oxygen vacancies near the surface, in agreement with the PL results (Fig. 34b). Upon annealing at higher temperatures (>250 °C), the intensity of the Ob peak reduced significantly, suggesting the annealing out of the oxygen vacancies from the surface of the NRs.

b) Hydrogen and Nitrogen defects:

The presence of these two defects has a minor effect on the photocatalytic degradation of water organic contaminants comparing to the oxygen and zinc defects covered in the precedent part, yet their presence is investigated briefly as follows:

Unlike other semiconductors (where hydrogen is amphoteric, i.e., occurs as H⁺ in p-type material and H⁻ in n-type material), hydrogen in ZnO is always positive, i.e., always acts as a donor. Hydrogen is tightly bound to an oxygen atom in ZnO, forming an O-H bond with a length of about 1.0 Å [147].

In n-type ZnO, the formation energy for hydrogen is only 1.56 eV. In p-type ZnO, incorporation of hydrogen is even more favorable. In fact, this may be beneficial for obtaining p-type ZnO. Indeed, incorporation of hydrogen during growth may increase acceptor solubility and suppress formation of compensating defects, similar to the behavior of hydrogen during doping of GaN with Mg acceptor. Then, the problem may reduce to removal of hydrogen during a post growth annealing.

Among all the candidates for p-type doping, nitrogen was predicted to be the shallowest acceptor in ZnO [193]. Yan et al. has demonstrated that while NO is a shallow acceptor, (N₂O) is a double-shallow donor, and competition between N and N₂ during doping of ZnO with N controls the doping type. These authors suggest that the use of N₂ or N₂O gas is not effective in p-type doping since energy must be supplied to break the strong N–N bond. It contrasts, NO or NO₂ molecules can readily form NO acceptors, taking advantage of the fact that O atoms are host atoms.

Doping agents:

We mentioned in the beginning of part 3 that our semiconductor band gap limits the photocatalytic activity (ZnO cannot absorb the visible region of the sun light which is ~45% of the solar spectrum). Another obstacle is surface and volumetric charge recombination that hinders heterogeneous photocatalysis to be an efficient purification method. So, the efforts have started to dope the most used semiconductor with metals and transition metals like (Fe³⁺, Mo⁵⁺, Ru³⁺, Os³⁺, Re⁵⁺, V⁴⁺, Rh³⁺, Co³⁺, Al³⁺...) in an effort to lower the transition energy (band gap) and the most widely studied semiconductor was TiO₂, but, all the efforts of doping and coupling of TiO₂ to tune its band gap for photocatalysis under visible light illumination were unsuccessful and have motivated us to dope ZnO with metal and transition metals for the reduction of organic compounds under visible light [194].

Thus, ZnO has more numbers of active sites with high surface reactivity [195] and it has been demonstrated as an improved photocatalyst as compared to commercialized TiO₂ based on its absorption efficacy of solar radiations [196].

However, ZnO has almost the same band gap (3.2 eV) as TiO₂. Surface area and surface defects play an important role in the photocatalytic activities of metal oxide. The reason is that, doping of metal oxide with metal and/or transition metals increases the surface defects [197] in addition it affects the optical and electronic properties [198] and can presumably shift the optical absorption towards the visible region. This can subsequently activate these modified metal oxide photocatalysts upon visible light irradiation.

There are reports of the enhancement of optical absorption in ZnO by doping with transition metal ions such as Ag, Pb, and Mn.

a) Ag doping:

C. Ren et al in 2010 has prepared in his study ZnO/Ag nanorods array (ZnO NRA) [199] in order to investigate the effect of doping ZnO NR with silver, thus, the optical properties of his Ag-doped ZnO semiconductor were examined using UV-Vis spectroscopy Fig. 36. In this figure it can be seen that the pure ZnO (band gap 3.37 eV) showed a steep absorption at wavelength shorter than 380 nm, and the silver addition did not make any significant difference in its band gap. This result was also confirmed by R. Kumar et al in 2015 when he showed that the band gap of the ZnO has not changed after being doped with Ag [200].

FIG.36 UV-Vis absorption spectrum of pure ZnO NRA (black) and Ag/ZnO NRA (red) with an AgNO₃ concentration of 0.05 M (AgNO₃ was used as a source of Ag in the preparation of Ag-doped ZnO) [199].

But the photodegradation activity of this doped semiconductor has shown different results. Therefore, the authors have checked the photocatalytic performance of the Ag/ZnO NRA with different Ag contents for degradation of MB Fig. 37. Thus, this figure shows the photodegradation ratio of different samples after 1 h irradiation.

FIG.37 The $\ln(C_0/C)$ versus time curves of photodegradation of MB. C_0 and C are the initial concentration after the adsorption equilibrium and the reaction concentration of MB, respectively. The experimental data are fitted using the pseudo-first-order kinetic equation: $\ln(C_0/C) = kt$. [199].

It can be seen that the loading of silver can significantly enhance the photocatalytic efficiency of ZnO in degradation of MB. The percentage degradation varied from 36.2% to 49.3% for different concentrations of AgNO_3 solution. It can be seen that the photocatalytic activity of these samples vary in the following order: pure ZnO < ZnO/Ag (0.02 M) < ZnO/Ag (0.05 M) > ZnO/Ag (0.1 M) > ZnO/Ag (0.2 M), it is found that the molar content of 0.37% (the concentration of AgNO_3 aqueous solution is 0.05 M) is the best dosage to achieve the highest photodegradation rate, so the optimal Ag loading for achieving the highest photocatalytic activity is 0.37 at.%. When the Ag loading is higher than this level, the photocatalytic activity will decrease with increasing Ag loading. The positive effect of noble metal deposits is commonly explained by the opinion that Ag nanoparticles on the semiconductor surface behave like electron sinks, which provide sites for accumulation of the photogenerated electrons, and then improve the separation of electrons and holes. This can be understood based on the proposed charge separation of Ag/ZnO under UV illumination shown in Fig. 38.

FIG.38 (a) The band structures of Ag and ZnO junction and the Fermi energy level equilibrium [201-203] without UV irradiation. (b) The proposed charge separation process and the photocatalytic mechanism of as-prepared Ag/ZnO samples under UV irradiation. The electrons in the Ag sinks can be trapped by the chemisorbed O_2 and the hole can be captured by the surface hydroxyl [199].

Fig. 38 shows the band structures and the Fermi energy levels of Ag and ZnO junction. Because the Fermi energy level of Ag (E_{fm}) is higher than that of ZnO (E_{fs}), part of electrons transferred from Ag to ZnO until the two systems attained equilibrium and a new Fermi energy level (E_f) was formed. And because the bottom energy level of the conduction band of ZnO is higher than the new equilibrium Fermi level (E_f) of Ag/ZnO, the photoexcited electrons on the conduction band could transfer from ZnO

to Ag nanoparticles. Therefore, Ag nanoparticles, acting as electron sinks, reduce the recombination of photoinduced electrons and holes, and improve the photocatalytic activity. On the other hand, more Ag particles loading will cover more semiconductor surface, inhibit UV irradiation to the interface of the Ag/ZnO, besides, silver particles also act as recombination centers at high silver deposition which leads to the decrease of the photocatalytic activity.

b) Mn doping:

R. Ullah, J. Dutta in their paper in 2008 [194] has prepared colloidal Mn-doped ZnO to investigate the effect of this atom when doping the zinc oxide. Thus, the optical properties were studied and a UV-Vis spectroscopy of the solution has been done Fig. 39.

FIG.39 UV-Vis absorption of ZnO, ZnO:Mn²⁺, represents difference in the optical absorption of Mn-doped and undoped ZnO, which indicate that Mn ion can generate more active site for reaction at energy level lower than the conduction band of undoped ZnO and thus absorbs visible light via these defect sites causing enhancement in the optical absorption of ZnO [194].

So, fig. 39 shows huge difference in the optical absorption of ZnO and ZnO:Mn²⁺ that demonstrates that manganese-doped ZnO (ZnO:Mn²⁺) absorbs more visible light and therefore can be used as an efficient photocatalyst under visible light irradiation.

The authors assume based on Wang et al and Vanhesuden et al that the enhancement in the optical absorption of ZnO:Mn²⁺ is due to the increase of defect sites in the crystal structure of the doped ZnO when compared to the undoped ZnO, as illustrated [197, 198]. In this case the optimum dopant (Mn) concentration was found to be 1%. This is because reduction in the optical absorption was observed upon further increase in the dopant concentration. Thus, the authors also assume that at high dopant concentration Mn²⁺ may react more readily with oxygen to form MnO_x instead of taking interstitial or substitutional site in ZnO crystal.

Therefore, Doping of ZnO with Mn²⁺ adds tail states in the vicinity of the valence band owing to the defect sites and reduces its effective band gap. This decrease in the band gap confirmed also by Bashi et al [201] which subsequently causes red shift in the optical absorption of Mn²⁺-doped ZnO nano/microfilms [202] and nanoparticles [203]. Upon irradiation with UV-Vis light electron-hole pair is generated within the effective band gap, i.e., electron transition takes place from the defect valence state to the defect conduction state. This transition within the tail states requires smaller excitation energy as compared to the native band gap (3.2 eV) of ZnO depending upon the particular dopant level within the band gap.

The photocatalytic activity of the doped ZnO was investigated using methylene blue (MB) as a dye for the photodegradation process in both UV range and Visible range separately Fig.40.

FIG.40 a) Photo-reduction of MB with ZnO and visible light, b) Photo-reduction of MB with ZnO:Mn²⁺ and visible light [194].

Fig. 40 shows that doped ZnO degrades the MB faster than the undoped one when irradiated under visible light. So, here the authors have assumed that upon illumination with visible light, ZnO:Mn²⁺ generates electron-hole pair at the tail states of conduction band and valence band, respectively. The generated electron transfers to the adsorbed MB molecule on the particle surface because it is a cationic dye. The excited electron from the photocatalyst conduction band enters into the molecular structure of MB and disrupts its conjugated system which then leads to the complete decomposition of MB. Hole at the valence band generates •OH via reaction with water or OH⁻ might be used for oxidation of other organic compounds

3.4 Stability

Rudakova et al in 2016 has studied the effect of the solution's PH on ZnO nano-coated over SiO₂-coated glasses [204]. Therefore, the authors evaluated the solubility of the ZnO nano-films occurring during the wetting and irradiation steps and the amount of Zn²⁺ ions due to dissolution of the ZnO nano-coating in water with different pH were analyzed using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy.

Ultrapure water was taken as a Zn²⁺ reference. The amounts of zinc ions transited from the ZnO surface of nano-coating into the water solution are presented in Table 1.

pH	Amount of Zn ²⁺ ions, ions/cm ²		
	after wetting for 40 min	in the dark for 20 min	after irradiation for 20 min
3.0	12000·10 ¹⁵ ±35·10 ¹⁵ (±0.2%)	-	-
5.5	1300·10 ¹⁵ ±17·10 ¹⁵ (±1.5%)	6000·10 ¹³ ±9·10 ¹³ (±0.1%)	610·10 ¹³ ±9·10 ¹³ (±1.4%)
10.0	130·10 ¹⁵ ±17·10 ¹⁵ (±6.5%)	-	-

Table 1 Amount of Zn²⁺ ions due to dissolution of the ZnO nano-coating in water with different pH for 40 min, and due to following irradiation of the ZnO nano-coating by full light of the 150 W Xe lamp for 20 min (for comparison, after storage of the ZnO nanocoating in the dark for 20 min), in Zn²⁺ ions per cm² of the ZnO coating [204].

According to the aforementioned table, the lower pH value of the aqueous solution corresponds to a faster ZnO dissolution. The maximum solubility of the ZnO coatings was found at pH of 3.0. That is by one and two orders of magnitude higher than its solubility in the water with pH of 5.5 and 10.0, respectively.

These data state that approximately one Zn²⁺ monolayer at the surface can be dissolved during one cycle with wetting in acidic water solution. The dissolution behavior for ZnO nano-coating can be explained by the following mechanism. Under the acidic conditions (pH < 7.0), a proton directly reacts with ZnO surface to facilitate the Zn²⁺ ion release, and the dissolved Zn²⁺ ions remain in the form of Zn²⁺ and Zn(OH)⁺ in solution or surface hydroxylated layers [205].

At pH is equal to 9.0 or higher, ZnO is dissolved in the form of the Zn(OH)₂,

Zn(OH)³⁻ and Zn(OH)^{4²⁻} hydroxyl complexes:

More specifically, hydroxyl complexes are mainly formed at the particle surface and result in minor dissolution. Also, these hydroxyl complexes can transform into the solid phase, and the Zn–O–Zn bonds are constructed due to dehydration reaction of more acidic bridged OH groups on the ZnO surface and O⁻ ions from the water solution [206].

Where n = 2 or 4.

Therefore, the formation and stabilization of the wurtzite ZnO phase on the top of the nano-coating is expected at pH values higher than value of isoelectric point (pH > 8.0).

Chapter 4: experimental photodegradation Microplastics using a ZnO NRs semiconductor

The aim of this work consisted of synthesizing and characterizing of visible light active zinc oxide nanorods (ZnO NRs) (following the hydrothermal growth method [207]) for being applied in photocatalytic degradation for cleaning marine litter, wherein the visible light absorption is enhanced by a Tin Oxide coating (SnOx). Methylene Blue had been used as an organic model to study the different photodegradation aspects.

The role of the coating is to provide stability for our semiconductor in acidic PH since ZnO is well known to be unstable in acidic medium and to have Zn(II) present in the solution in the form of Zn^{2+} ions or soluble complex $Zn(OH)^+$ at $pH < 8$ or $Zn(OH)_4^{2-}$ at $pH > 13$ [208] and to enhance the degradation of organic molecule by profiting from the energy bands level of both; ZnO and SnOx; at the ZnO/SnOx heterojunction to assure the required flow of charge carrier (electrons and holes) between ZnO and SnOx particles (ZnO has his native band gap (of 3.2 eV) [209] in the Ultraviolet region (UV), however, solar spectrum consists unfortunately of only 5–7% of UV light, while 46% and 47% of the spectrum has visible light and infrared radiation, respectively [210]).

Therefore, this work include two parts:

1. Photocatalytic activity
2. PH stability test

Results provide a simple strategy to make the wide bandgap ZnO NRs visible light active, enabling their use as promising semiconductors for photocatalytic decontamination of waste water.

Experimental part

4.1 Materials

Zinc acetate dihydrate ($Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$) from Aldrich, USA,
Zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$) from Aldrich, USA,
Hexamethylenetetramine ($(CH_2)_6N_4$) from Aldrich, USA,
Methylene blue ($C_{16}H_{18}ClN_3S \cdot xH_2O$) from Aldrich, USA,
Coumarin $C_9H_6O_2$ from Aldrich, USA,
Ammonium hexafluorostannate ($(NH_4)_2SnF_6$) from Aldrich, USA,
Urea ($CO(NH_2)_2$) from MERCK, Germany,
Standard microscope glass slides were used as substrates for the growth of ZnO NRs,

4.2 Experimental details

a) synthesis of ZnO NRs coated glass substrate

ZnO nanorods were grown hydrothermally on microscope glass substrates; therefore, the substrates were pre-cleaned by successive sonication in soap water, ethanol, acetone and deionized (DI) water for 15 minutes each and dried in an oven until further use. A ZnO seed layer was deposited on the cleaned

substrates using spray pyrolysis of 10 mM zinc acetate $[\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ in DI water at a rate of 1 mL/min (from a distance of 20 cm) on the cleaned substrates pre-heated to 350 °C.

FIG.41 (a) substrates cleaning process in a VWR ultrasonic cleaner (b) seeding process using spray pyrolysis on glass substrates heated at 350 °C.

The seeded substrates were subsequently placed in a chemical bath containing equimolar (10mM) concentration of zinc nitrate hexahydrate $(\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and Hexamethylenetetramine $((\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4)$ in DI water.

Then, they were placed in a commercial microwave oven (Sharp, Low Mode) for 5 hours, wherein the precursor solution was replenished every 60 minutes (fast method). Therefore, the prepared batches were annealed at 100, 250, 350 and 500 °C.

FIG.42 (a) annealing the sample at 100, 250, 350 and 500 °C in the furnace, (b) prepared equimolar batches of zinc nitrate hexahydrate and hexamine.

b) Coating ZnO NRs with tin oxide

A solution of 0.01 mol/L of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SnF}_6$ in DI water was prepared and another solution of 0.1

mol/L of Urea in Ethanol was also prepared. The two solutions were mixed together with a volume of 1:4. Then, the ZnO nanorods were immersed in a bath containing the two mixed solutions already prepared as we described earlier and the bath was heated to 90 °C for 30 minutes. After the reaction took place the nanorods was washed with DI water and dried for further use.

The dissociation of ammonium hexafluorostannate in water has given an acidic PH; and as it was mentioned, an acidic PH will have harmful consequences on our ZnO NRs according to the following reactions [211]:

Therefore adding the solution of Urea in Ethanol, it was expected to increase the PH through the following reactions [212]:

Therefore the adding Urea will dissociate to give an NH₃ which is known to react with H⁺, hence the resulted proton from reaction (1) will be prevented from reacting with our ZnO.

c) Characterization

Morphology of the ZnO NRs was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Model: FEG-SEM: Ultra 55, ZEISS) operated at 3 kV.

Optical properties where recorded using both fluorecence spectrometer (LS55 from Perkin Elmer, Italy) to record the different emission wavelength in order to compare them and figure out new peaks related to defect states and UV/Vis spectrometer (Lamda 750 from Perkin Elmer, Italy) to measure the absorption of different made semiconductor .

FIG.43 (a) scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Model: FEG-SEM: Ultra 55, ZEISS) operated at 3 kV, (b) Optical properties where recorded using a fluorecence spectrometer (LS 55 from Perkin Elmer, Italy), (c) UV/Vis spectrometer (Lamda 750 from Perkin Elmer, Italy)

a)

b)

c)

d)

e)

f)

g)

h)

i)

j)

k)

l)

m)

FIG.44 (a) (PL) spectra of the ZnO NRs obtained with excitation wavelength of 325 nm, (b) Room temperature UV/Vis optical absorption of ZnO, (c) variation in the visible emission peaks from the ZnO NRs annealed at different temperatures, (d) variation in the visible emission green peak from the ZnO NRs annealed at different temperatures, (e) Comparative (PL) spectra of the ZnO NRs and ZnO/SnOx obtained with excitation wavelength of 325 nm, (f) Room temperature comparative UV/Vis optical absorption of ZnO and ZnO/SnOx, (g) (h) Scanning Electron micrograph (SEM) of ZnO NRs showing the microstructure before being coated, (i) (j) Scanning Electron micrograph (SEM) of ZnO NRs showing the microstructure after being coated, (k) TEM images taken for 30 minutes coating, (l) 60 minutes coating, (m) 90 minutes coating.

d) Photocatalytic test

The photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) was performed under natural sunlight and under a Halogen lamp (Co-Tech ECLC-HALO-0103D 150 W) as well, to compare the effect of the two light sources, using the ZnO NRs on glass substrates (supported photocatalysts) annealed at different temperatures and then repeated the photocatalytic test after coating the same set of catalysts.

All the natural sunlight experiments were conducted on partly sunny days during 10:00 – 15:00 hrs. Thus, a 10 μ M aqueous solution of MB was placed along with a ZnO NR substrate (3 cm \times 1 cm) inside polystyrene Petri dishes, with the photocatalyst surface facing the light source. Following equilibration under dark conditions for 1 h, photocatalytic degradation of MB was carried out under light for 180 min.

All halogen light experiments were conducted in poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) cuvettes, radiated directly by the halogen lamp and with light intensity fixed to half sun.

e) Analytical method

Visible light photocatalytic reduction of MB was monitored by recording the optical absorption spectra of the MB solution at regular intervals by placing the poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) cuvettes in a UV/Vis spectrometer (Lambda 750 from Perkin Elmer, Italy). The concentration of MB was estimated from the reduction in absorption intensity of MB at $\lambda_{\max} = 663$ nm and plotted as C_t/C_0 versus time, where C_t represents the concentration of MB at time 't' and C_0 represents the initial concentration of MB. A first order exponential equation ($y = ae^{-bx}$) was used to fit the MB decay curves, where 'a' is a pre-exponential factor and 'b' represents the degradation rate constant in min^{-1} [213]. Thus, the absorption is measured according to Beer-Lambert law:

$$A = \epsilon bc$$

Where A is the absorbance (no unit), ϵ is the molar absorptivity with units of $\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, b is the path length of the sample; we will express this measurement in centimeters.

c is the concentration of the compound in solution, expressed in mol.L^{-1} . So, as the concentration C is proportional to the absorbance we can directly use A/A_0 which is equal to C_t/C_0 to plot the concentration decay curve.

This decay curve appears to follow the following formula:

$$C/C_0 = ae^{-bt}$$

$$\ln(C/C_0) = - (ab)t = -kt$$

Where k is the apparent degradation rate constant [214].

FIG.45 (a) photo which depict the photodegradation experiment in sunlight, it could be seen here, the taking of aliquots from each samples to be measured in the UV/Vis spectrometer, (b) Photodegradation of MB under halogen light.

As we can see in Fig. 45 (a) the batches are placed under normal sunlight and all the batches are covered with a polystyrene cover to prevent water evaporation. Therefore, the absorption spectra of the polystyrene cover was measured to be in the UV region < 300 nm.

f) Result and discussion

I. ZnO NRs structure and defects

Scanning electron micrograph (SEM) of the prepared ZnO NRs show the characteristic hexagonal shape of the NRs which has been altered to take more a cylindrical shape after the coating with tin oxide (Fig. 44g-i). A closer look shows that the coating has been deposited as an island covering all the sharp edges of the native ZnO NRs.

Room temperature optical absorption and photoluminescence (PL) spectra of the ZnO NRs are shown in Fig. 44a-c-d. A strong absorption in the UV region was observed from the ZnO NRs due to the high UV absorption coefficient of ZnO, with very little absorption in the visible region.

The PL spectrum obtained with 325 nm excitation wavelength showed peaks in both UV and visible region Fig. 45. The peak at 390 nm is reported to be attributed to the radiative recombination of electrons captured in defect states (zinc interstitial (Zni) defects located at ~ 0.22 eV below the CB of ZnO) with the holes in the VB of ZnO [213]. Moreover, the two observed peaks at 533 and 585 nm were in accordance with the previous work by T. Bora, et al [213] where the transition of a photo-excited electron

from the CB of ZnO to a Vo^{++} center causes the 533 nm emission, while the recombination of a captured electron from Vo^+ state to a VB hole leads to the 585 nm emission.

FIG.46 Blue and green emissions of ZnO NRs.

Fig. 44d shows the variations in the emission bands of ZnO NRs with different annealing temperatures. In this work, annealing up to 350 °C, instead of 250 °C give the optimum intensity of the green emission which was found to increase, indicating an increase in the defect density on the NR surface. This difference, between our optimum temperature and the reported temperature previously [213], can be referred to the ZnO NRs synthesis parameters which alter the oxygen defects probably in the growing stage which was performed here in a commercial microwave.

Hence, Fig. 44f shows that the UV/Vis absorbance spectra tend to be lower for the coated ZnO nanorods which may reflect in the photocatalytic activity later.

Room temperature photoluminescence (PL) spectrum of the obtained ZnO/SnO NRs are measured with UV light excitation at 325 nm. Fig. 44e shows an emission spectra at 390 nm (3.18 eV), and a strong emission at 500nm (the 390 nm emission for SnO coincides with the 390 emission of the radiative

recombination of electrons captured in defect states; zinc interstitial (Zni) defects located at ~ 0.22 eV below the CB of ZnO; with the holes in the VB of ZnO [213]). SnO is a p-type semiconductor with a wide optical band gap of 2.7-3.4 eV. So, the ultraviolet PL peak at 390 nm (3.18 eV) is possibly attributed to the band edge emission of SnO [214].

II. ZnO NRs for visible light photocatalytic degradation of Microplastics

Methylene Blue had been used as an organic model to study the different photodegradation aspects. The photodegradation of MB (blue in color) to LMB (colorless) was observed by monitoring the MB peak absorption (663 nm) upon continued light exposure [215].

a)

b)

FIG.47 Photodegradation of MB over ZnO NRs annealed at different temperature using (a) halogen lamp, (b) sunlight

Fig. 47 shows the photocatalytic degradation efficiency of MB in term of C_t/C_0 [%] with ZnO NRs differently annealed. An increase in the MB degradation percentage was observed with increasing annealing temperatures up to 350 °C, while upon annealing at temperatures higher than 350 °C, the degradation was found to be lower. This suggests a direct relationship between visible light photocatalytic activity and surface defect states on ZnO NRs. Typically defect states improve the optical absorption by allowing sub-bandgap transitions and generating active e–h pairs under visible light irradiation [216], which can be transferred to the surface adsorbed MB molecules, thus increasing the electron transfer rate with increasing surface defects [179, 217].

The photo-excited electrons in ZnO can transfer to the surface adsorbed MB molecules through non-radiative transition which is controlled by the existing defects on the ZnO surface.

However, when NRs are annealed at temperatures higher than 350 °C, reduction in the surface defects limits the electron transfer process from ZnO surface defects to MB molecules; in turn reducing the photocatalytic degradation efficiency considerably for the 500 °C, annealed ZnO NRs.

Radiating the MB sample over ZnO NRs with sunlight has increased the degradation percentage from 70% in halogen lamp to 82%. This increasing of 12% clearly refers to a direct relationship between the photocatalytic activity of synthesized ZnO and % of UV natively existing in normal sunlight [218].

The photocatalytic activity of the coated ZnO NRs with tin oxide was also tested with MB and the degradation curves was plotted versus time in Fig. 48. Thus, the results of the same set of ZnO NRs annealed at 100°C, 250°C, 350°C, 500°C, then coated with SnOx, then re-annealed at 100°C, 250°C,

350°C, 500°C, show expect of part b); where the coated set was re-annealed at 250°C; that as expected, re-annealing this set at higher temperature makes the degradation efficiency percentage closer as the temperature increases till 500°C.

The other obtained results, is that the degradation percentage of the coated ZnO NRs decreased from 41% for T=100°C to 33% for T=250°C than increased a little bit of 36% for T=350°C and remained the same for T=500°C.

As it is well known that SnO₂ starts to form above 600°C, (so what we have at lower temperature is mainly SnO with a mixture of SnO₂, Sn₂O₃, Sn₃O₄, however, in very smaller concentration [2219, 220]) the obvious decrease in the efficiency can be attributed to the decrease in oxygen vacancies due the oxidation of SnO while annealed in air for one hour at T=250°C. [221-223]. Since these vacancies are the electron donors in the n-type SnO_x semiconductor, the free-electron concentration is expected to decrease too [224] and as the MB accepts electron and starts its degradation [215], annealing at temperatures above 250°C will reflect in a decrease in the photocatalytic activity of the ZnO/SnO NRs. Hence, a small increase in this activity appears at T=350°C and T=500°C due to a small enhancement in the crystallinity of the amorphous SnO.

The result of the same photodegradation experiment under sun light Fig. 49 is in accordance with the previous results where halogen lamp was used. Hence the UV/Vis absorbance of the same ZnO/SnO_x substrate annealed at different temperature 100°C, 250°C, 350°C, 500°C, Fig. 50 shows a higher absorbance at T=100°C, then decreases from T=250°C to be nearly the same for T=350°C, only T=500°C shows a different behavior which is lower from 363 nm to 354 nm the increases rapidly to overcome the others.

a)

b)

c)

d)

FIG.48 (a) Photodegradation curve of ZnO NRs annealed at 100°C,250°C,350°C,500°C, then coated with SnOx, then re-annealed at 100°C, under halogen lamp (b) Photodegradation curve of ZnO NRs annealed at 100°C,250°C,350°C,500°C, then coated with SnOx, then re-annealed at 250°C, under halogen lamp (c) Photodegradation curve of ZnO NRs annealed at 100°C,250°C,350°C,500°C, then coated with SnOx, then re-annealed at 350°C, under halogen lamp (d) Photodegradation curve of ZnO NRs annealed at 100°C,250°C,350°C,500°C, then coated with SnOx, then re-annealed at 500°C, under halogen lamp.

FIG.49 Photodegradation curve of ZnO/SnOx NRs annealed at 100°C, 250°C, 350°C and 500°C, under sun light.

FIG.50 UV/Vis absorbance of ZnO/SnOx annealed at 100°C, 250°C, 350°C, and 500°C.

FIG.51 Energy band of ZnO NRs coated with SnO after irradiation with a light source [225].

The concept behind enhancing ZnO NRs photocatalytic activity with SnO coating, is illustrated in Fig. 51. Thus, having the SnO coating on the outer shell of ZnO and irradiating the ZnO/SnO NR will cause the excited electrons on the conduction band (CB) of SnO to move to a lower energy conduction band at the ZnO/SnO heterojunction, which is the ZnO CB in this case. In the opposite, the created holes in ZnO valence band (VB), will move to the SnO VB as they have tendency to move to a higher energy band. The result will be a higher holes concentration at the SnO coating surface and lesser electrons concentrations in this surface.

This interpretation will result in a decrease in the MB degradation percentage from using ZnO NRs alone to ZnO/SnO NRs, as MB is known to accept electrons degrades into leucomethylene [215] which is in accordance with the result shown in Fig. 52. However, when a hole acceptor like coumarin [226] is used it is expected to have the opposite, higher degradation % for ZnO/SnO than ZnO alone, which is also in accordance in the result of Fig. 53. Coumarin reacts with $\bullet\text{OH}$ to produce umbelliferone [226]. Thus, photocatalytic degradation of Coumarin was monitored by recording the fluorescence spectra of the 10 mM solution of coumarin versus time by placing the catalysts (ZnO and ZnO/SnO) in poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) cuvettes in a fluorescence spectrometer (LS 55 from Perkin Elmer, Italy). The concentration of umbelliferone was estimated from the emission wave intensity at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 450\text{nm}$ and plotted as $[(C_t/C_o) \times 100 - 100]$ versus time, where C_t represents the concentration of umbelliferone at time 't' and C_o represents the initial concentration of umbelliferone.

FIG. 52 Photodegradation curve of ZnO and ZnO/SnOx NRs under sun light.

FIG. 53 The concentration of umbelliferone generated in 10 mM coumarin in presence of ZnO and ZnO/SnO, was plotted as a function of the irradiation time, under halogen light.

III. ZnO and ZnO/SnO stability in acidic PH

In order to apply a long term photodegradation using ZnO NRs the PH stability of this last one must be enhanced (it is well known that ZnO dissolve to Zn^{2+} in an acidic PH) [227]. The second target in coating ZnO with SnO was to provide this stability by preventing the dissolution of ZnO into Zn^{2+} , or at least to slow the rate of this dissolution.

Thus, this concept was tested by placing ZnO substrates in three different PH: 6 and 2 as well as placing the coated ZnO substrates in the same PH. The dissolution curves of each in each PH for both substrates was monitored versus time in Fig. 54. Thus, at each time interval a sample was taken from all the solution and tested in the ICP spectrometer (iCAP 6000 Series) to measure the dissolution of Zn^{2+} . Therefore, $[(Ct/Co) \times 100]$ was plotted versus time where Ct refers to the concentration of Zn^+ at time “t” and Co refers to the its concentration at initial time.

a)

b)

FIG. 54 Dissolution curve of ZnO and ZnO/SnO at (a) PH=6,(b) PH=2

The results shows an enhancing in the dissolution rate for PH=6 for the coated ZnO NRs. For PH=2 both substrates where almost completely dissolved after merely 30 minutes, however, ZnO/SnO has shown a slightly little enhancement. In normal case SnO should be stable till PH=4 and thus protect the ZnO NRs from corrosion [228].

Conclusion

ZnO NRs were grown hydrothermally on glass substrates and used for visible light photocatalysis under simulated solar light. It was observed that annealing the NRs up to 250 °C in the ambient leads to an increase in the concentration of defect states near the surface of the ZnO NRs (surface defects), whereupon a further increase in annealing temperature can passivate the surface defects. Photoluminescence studies indicate that the surface defects are mostly in the form of oxygen vacancies, where a direct correlation between the surface defect density and the visible light photocatalytic degradation of MB as model organic dye and non-dye contaminants can be observed. The enhanced visible light photocatalytic activity of the ZnO NRs is primarily attributed to the defect states present near the surface of the NRs, which improves e–h pair generation through sub-bandgap absorption of visible light.

ZnO nanorods were coated then with tin oxide. The photocatalytic activity of the ZnO and ZnO/SnO was tested under halogen light and sun light with both, 10 μM aqueous solution of MB and 10 μM aqueous solution of coumarin. It was found that the photodegradation efficiency of ZnO/SnO was less than that of ZnO in MB and higher than that of ZnO in coumarin. The science behind that is that the coating creates a pool of holes at the outer surface where the SnO exists and resulting in higher generation of •OH. At the same time sucking the exited electrons to the inner shell of ZnO. Dissolution curves of both ZnO and ZnO/SnO were plotted at different PH and Tin Oxide was found to protect the ZnO from corrosion.

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